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**EFFECTIVENESS OF COLLABORATIVE TECHNO-ENHANCED
ANCHORED INSTRUCTION AND LEARNING STYLES ON SOCIAL
SKILLS AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS**

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ABSTRACT

Secondary Schools are the primary centers where young minds are shaped; consequently shaping the destiny of a nation with constructive societal changes. Quality Secondary School Science education should make youth display characteristics of being knowledgeable, confident, civilized and global minded. Physics being a complex, abstract and mathematical branch of Science, Physics learning in Secondary School is said to develop academic and lifelong utilizable Social Skills that can be utilized in most situations of life. Students with high Social Skills are said to foster building up of a community that collaboratively works towards social and economic progress. Thus, along with academic achievement, Secondary Schools must give equal priority to developing essential Social Skills. However, in this technology driven world, where adolescents face conflicts academically, emotionally, psychologically and socially and Physics educators are laden with immense amount of scholastic and non-scholastic work, today's educators constantly face a challenge of purposefully employing ways and means to develop and Nurture Social Skills. Rather than focusing on development of academic and Social Skills separately, the best possible way could be integrating the development of Social Skills into everyday teaching-learning using innovative pedagogies. One such technology-based Constructivist Instructional Method that successfully assists in developing Social Skills among Secondary School students is Collaborative Techno-Enhanced Anchored Instruction (CTEAI) in Physics. Highlighting the concept of Collaborative Techno-Enhanced Anchored Instruction and Social Skills, this paper portrays the results of an experimental study which intends to investigate the effectiveness of Collaborative Techno-Enhanced Anchored Instruction and Learning Styles on Social Skills among Secondary School students. The educational

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implications facilitate educators to adopt humanistic approach to Physics Education and help stake holders to undertake suitable initiatives for appropriate infusion of innovative ICT enhanced teaching-learning strategies that enhance Social Skills among Secondary School students.

Keywords - Anchored Instruction, Social Skills, Learning Styles, Secondary School students, ICT Enhanced Science Instruction

Introduction

It is an irrefutable fact that, a nation finds solution to its problems in relation to its achievement in education; moreover education lays foundation for its economic progress, moral regeneration and revival of its people (Kingdom & Mackie, 2013). Secondary Schools are primary centers for acquiring academic excellence as well as essential life skills. With each student being unique in his ability, Learning Styles and social background, diverse experiences in Secondary School helps students acquire lifelong utilizable Social Skills as a part of their schooling. Physics Education when suitably integrated with Information and Communication Technology (ICT) and Constructive learning strategies is said to promote academic success, develop Social Skills and foster over-all wellbeing of young adolescents. With this standpoint, the present study aimed to investigate the effectiveness of a novel Constructivist Instructional Method named Collaborative Techno-Enhanced Anchored Instruction (CTEAI) and Learning Styles on Social Skills among Secondary School Pupils.

Need, Significance and Rationale of the study:

In this rapidly changing world, an adolescent's life is highly challenging and demanding. Studying with peers of different ability levels, family backgrounds and social status, young teenagers not only learn reading, writing and math in schools, but unknowingly familiarize themselves with both positive and negative experiences of life. Additionally, academic competition, family pressures where teenagers are expected to show adult-type independence in study habits and organized way of carrying out daily activities, while no permission is given to act older in terms of dress, friendship or use of technology; generation gaps, identity crisis, constant comparisons, abuse of social media and peer demands may cause academic, emotional, social and psychological stress leading to behavioral problems. Affinity towards digital devices also separates them from real-world interactions and social life.

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All students are born with certain innate social competencies. As they grow, these social competencies become their strength to adapt to constantly changing experiences and environment. Encountering the aforementioned challenges, the associated uncertainties and complexities make adolescents answer the tests of social life constantly, based on their Social Skills. Passing these social life tests can become motivating experience for some students who have strong family background. For many who do not receive corrections, guidance and support at the right time, it may be a devastating experience, hampering their social connectedness, causing an irreparable damage to self-esteem, leading to loss of sensitivity to problems and reduction of academic, personal and social efficiency. When ignored, problems of youth aggravate into bigger problems as adults. The biggest challenge for educators today is reaching out to each child’s academic and personality development needs. Hence, along with the academics, developing, strengthening and nurturing lifetime useable Social Skills among Secondary students is an immediate need and vital inevitability; the finest way being incorporating them into regular teaching-learning process.

Aikenhead (2006) has asserted that canonical science is very hard to use in everyday life. A study of past literature identifies some drawbacks of traditional Science teaching which includes limited opportunity to understand the importance of knowledge acquired in classrooms in finding solution for everyday problems; and knowledge being inert that cannot be explicitly and spontaneously used in problem-solving situation (Baumbach, Brewer & Bird, 2000;

Bransford et. al, 1990). Physics being a complex, abstract and mathematical branch of Science, Physics teaching-learning process in Secondary Schools is fixed, time-bound and focused primarily at acquiring factual knowledge, thus taught in isolation of daily life situations in most classrooms. Most students consider Physics as tough and abstract since they cannot relate their learning to day-to-day living. Physics curriculum of Secondary Schools in Karnataka is vast and intense consisting of both simple and abstract topics. Each class is non-streamed with students of mixed ability levels and diverse Learning Styles undergoing mass instruction. Although teachers are very well qualified, there is no measure of their teaching competence in providing engaging and challenging experiences that develops both academic and Social Skills of students. Due to pressure of completing unwieldy curriculum in relatively short stipulated time, over-emphasis on test-performance results, large student number, administrative work and class-management issues, most teachers find difficulty in implementing new and innovative instructional strategies

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that emphasize on developing Social Skills of students along with Science achievement.

Past literature asserts that young individuals must be educated to become citizens who possess understanding of local issues, learn to put up with diversity in thought, develop culture of healthy argument and an open-mind to change opinions to reach best reasoned judgment as to which course of action will solve problems, which can be materialized by giving educational opportunity that can engage them in collective decision-making about complex and critical social problems (Johnson & Johnson, 2000). Creating links between classroom activity and real world develops self-management, problem solving, critical and creative thinking, interpersonal relationship and effective communication; empathy, self-awareness and coping with stress and emotions (Chinwar, 2012; Ajithkumar, 2009 & Nair, 2013). Social Skills training when incorporated into Science teaches students the significance of discovering actual truth hidden in society, rather than believing false teachings (Denham et. al., 2007; Pawattana, Prasarnpanich & Attanawong, 2014). Fortifying Social Skills by collaborative learning has positive effect on adolescents' social functioning - it strengthens their identity in society, teaches to value human dignity and equality, better self-regulation and minimizes impulsive, aggressive or anti-social behaviors (Montroy, et. al., 2014). Students who are socially competent become accountable for their deeds and are more likely to experience school success than those who are not (Callahan et. al., 2009).

In addition, most past studies were conducted at preschool and primary level; not secondary level where youth benefit. Concept of Social Skills is prioritized in collegiate and entrepreneurship trainings under Management Studies, whereas investigator believes that these skills must be inculcated and deep-rooted in students at grass-root level - Secondary School. Teaching Physics in schools has been the dissemination of factual knowledge; no importance has been given to humanistic values and skills the subject can develop. The above discussions convincingly strengthen investigators assert that a change from traditional method of Physics education to technology-based constructivist instructional method is the need of the hour; thus this paper explores the effectiveness of Collaborative Techno-Enhanced Anchored Instruction in Physics against traditional methods, and Learning Styles on Social Skills among Secondary School students.

Objective of the study:

To study the main and interaction effect of Instructional Methods (Collaborative Techno-Enhanced Anchored Instruction and Lecture-Demonstration Method) and Learning styles on Social Skills of Secondary School Students after partialling out the effect of Intelligence.

Hypothesis of the Study:

There is no significant difference in the main and interaction effect of Instructional Methods (Collaborative Techno-Enhanced Anchored Instruction and Lecture-Demonstration Method) and Learning styles on Social Skills of Secondary School students after partialling out the effect of Intelligence.

Variables involved in the Study:

Independent variables:

Two independent variables were involved in the present study, namely Instructional Methods and Learning Styles.

(i) Instructional Methods:

1. Collaborative Techno-Enhanced Anchored Instruction:

In the present study, Collaborative Techno-Enhanced Anchored Instruction (CTEAI) refers to a student-centered, technology-based, constructivist teaching-learning approach adapted to Physics instruction which involves active participation of learners, working in small collaborative groups based on their Learning Styles that facilitates discussion and experimentation, using multimedia and ICT tools, to learn Physics concepts and principles, in the form of situated learning within complex, meaningful, realistic, integrated problem-solving context related directly or close to real-life, through six phases of CTEAI - Introduction (Introducing the anchor), Familiarization (Developing shared experience around the anchor), Expansion (Expanding the anchor), Construction (Using knowledge as tools for problem solving), Transfer (Working on projects related to anchor) and Sharing (Sharing knowledge). Learning activities are designed around an "Anchor" - a novel, structured, problem-based story, adventure, or situation, typically embedded with factual authentic real data needed for problem solving; learners play the role of an authentic (realistic) problem-solver, identifying problem, researching information needed to solve the problem, identifying gaps to their knowledge, and developing solutions; in the process

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discovering and learning the content of Physics with the aid of teacher scaffolding.

The Instructional Package on Collaborative-Techno Enhanced Anchored Instruction in Physics, used in the present study is prepared by the investigator based on the chapter "Heat" under Standard Nine Physics Syllabus according to Karnataka State Education Board.

2. Lecture-Demonstration Method:

In the present study, Lecture-Demonstration Method refers to the teacher-centered method of Physics instruction which involves active participation of teacher in teaching Physics concepts and principles to a large group of students, grouped based on their Learning Styles, through verbal delivery of content with a few illustrations and experiments/demonstrations wherever applicable, without the use of digital devices and ICT tools, through Herbartian Five Step Approach of Lesson Planning (Introduction, Presentation, Association or Comparison, Generalization and Application). Students receive the information as explanations through passive listening, occasionally answering questions individually with no scope for discussions, hands-on experiments and problem-solving.

The Instructional Package on Lecture-Demonstration Method in Physics, used in the present study is prepared by the investigator based on the chapter "Heat" under Standard Nine Physics Syllabus according to Karnataka State Education Board.

(ii) Learning Styles:

Learning Style is one's preferred mode of gaining knowledge, which involves a set of factors, behaviors and attitude that facilitates absorbing and retaining information in a given learning situation.

In the present study, McCarthy's Learning Styles - Imaginative, Common Sense and Dynamic Learning Styles are employed.

Imaginative Learners - Perceive information directly, process reflectively; feel and watch, seek personal associations, meaning and involvement. They ask "Why?"

Common Sense Learners - Perceive information abstractly, process by doing; experimenting, building and creating usability. They ask "How does it work?"

Dynamic Learners - Perceive information concretely/sensing feeling, process by doing; like challenging tasks, flexible and handle challenging situations easily. They ask "What if?"

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Learning Styles was measured by administering "The Learning Style Inventory", constructed by investigator as an adapted version of 4MAT Learning Style Quiz by McCarthy (1990).

Dependent Variable:

The dependent variable involved in the study is Social Skills which is defined as the ability of a student that enables him/her to successfully and effectively interact and communicate within himself/herself and also with other people or personalities. Being divided into two broad categories - Interpersonal Skills (communication skills, leadership skills, listening skills, conflict handling, flexible thinking and teamwork) and Intrapersonal Skills (self-management, self-motivation, personality, problem solving and time management), Social Skills in the present study are measured by administering the "Test on Social Skills", constructed by the Investigator.

Control Variables:

Pre-Achievement in Physics:

In the present study, Pre-Achievement in Physics is the marks obtained by IX Standard students in the multiple choice test called "Pre-Achievement Test in Physics", constructed by the investigator based on the Physics concepts considered to be the pre-requisite knowledge for the students to successfully learn the Physics content selected for the study.

Digital Literacy:

The Digital Literacy is defined as the minimum knowledge and ability of the Secondary School students to use digital technology, communication tools or networks to locate, evaluate, use and create information appropriate to their academic and age level. In the present study, Digital Literacy is measured by administering the "Digital Literacy Inventory" for Secondary School students constructed by the investigator.

Intelligence:

In the present study, Intelligence is measured by administering the standardized Intelligence Test named "Raven's Progressive Matrices (RPM)" developed by John C. Raven, based on Charles Spearman's theory of general intelligence, also known as 'g factor', that refers to the overall mental capacity that influences a person's performance on cognitive ability measures.

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Secondary School Students:

Students who are studying Physics as a part of prescribed Science syllabus by the Karnataka State Education Board in IX Standard are considered as Secondary School students.

Methodology:

The present study was an experimental research which involved 2X3 Factorial Design with Covariate having two independent variables. The first being Instructional Methods had two levels - CTEAI and Lecture-Demonstration Method. The second independent variable was Learning Styles which had three levels - Dynamic, Imaginative and Common Sense Learners. This design facilitated the investigator to manipulate two or more variables simultaneously, which provided two main effects and one interaction effect. Intelligence was treated as Covariate which was statistically controlled. Two homogenous experimental groups, each consisting of 103 students were formed randomly by matching their Digital Literacy and Pre-Achievement in Physics. Both the experimental groups were further grouped according to their Learning Styles, where 80 students underwent CTEAI and 72 students underwent Lecture-Demonstration Method.

The sample of the study comprised of a total of 206 students of Standard IX from Urban and Rural Schools of Virajpet Taluk, following Karnataka State Syllabus during the year 2017- 18, aged 14 to 16 years. The tools used for the study were Test on Social Skills, Digital Literacy Inventory, Pre-Achievement Test in Physics, Learning Styles Inventory and Instructional Packages on CTEAI and Lecture-Demonstration Method, all constructed by investigator. Standardized test - Raven's Progressive Matrices was used to measure Intelligence. Experimental data was analyzed and the hypothesis was tested using Two Way ANCOVA. The significance level was set to 0.05 levels.

Major Findings of the Study:

The result of the study to investigate the main and interaction effect of Instructional Methods - Collaborative Techno-Enhanced Anchored Instruction and Lecture-Demonstration Method and Learning styles on Social Skills of Secondary School Students after partialling out the effect of Intelligence are given below:

There is a significant difference in the effect of Instructional Methods on Social Skills of

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Secondary School Students after partialling out the effect of Intelligence. CTEAI is significantly more effective than Lecture-Demonstration Method in developing Social Skills among Secondary School Students.

1. There is no significant difference in the effect of Learning Styles (Common Sense, Dynamic and Imaginative Learners) on Social Skills of Secondary School Students after partialling out the effect of Intelligence. Thus, students with all Learning Styles are equal in Social Skills development.
2. Interaction effect of Instructional Methods and Learning Styles has no significant effect on Social Skills of Secondary School Students after partialling out the effect of Intelligence.

Educational Implications:

- ❖ Since CTEAI was more effective in developing Social Skills among Secondary School students than traditional methods and students with all Learning Styles were found to be equal in Social Skills development, the researcher urges and recommends that Physics teachers must make sincere efforts to step out of comfort zone of traditional teaching and make use of CTEAI for Physics Instruction.
- ❖ Since CTEAI focuses on Collaborative Learning, teachers can include activity-oriented classroom instruction like team-based practical and project work, role-play of social situations, group discussions, class games, cross-curricular activities and incidental teaching integrated within Science curriculum to improve Social Skills among students.
- ❖ Anchor in CTEAI can be based on real-world experiences and systematic analysis of daily-life problems, where selective activities can be employed to develop communication, cooperation, responsibility, empathy, open-mindedness and an eye for social problems.

As CTEAI involves working extensively in digital environment during Physics Instruction, it is evident that technology, when constructively and suitably integrated into teaching-learning process, develops Social Skills in students rather than detaching them from social environment. Schools must train students how to remain safe in digital environment and to use technology for constructive learning purposes. Schools also must educate parents through seminars and talks to help their children widen their knowledge by sharing their creative academic thoughts and ideas on social issues with experts using social media and collaboratively work towards social

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cause.

❖ School administrators must try to improve their institutional facilities like digital libraries, science laboratories, ICT labs and multimedia rooms, so that Physics teachers can successfully implement CTEAI in schools. Since CTEAI enforces problem-based learning, schools must provide opportunity for teachers to take students out of classrooms into the real world, to interact with people, identify problems and use scientific methods to solve them, thus developing both academic and humanistic approach to Physics learning. Physics Instruction thus, must teach students how to take initiative, involvement in situations, time management, use of assertive language and taking responsibility.

❖ Schools must train in-service teachers to implement CTEAI. In this regard, teachers must be trained to work in digital environments like using digital mind-mapping, wikis, e-books, educational games, online encyclopedias, e-libraries, online journals etc. Teacher training institutes must train prospective teachers to experiment with new trends of teaching-learning activities, so that they gain the confidence to use them in their professional life. Trainings must convincingly and realistically highlight the humanistic approach to Physics learning.

Conclusion:

Providing quality and skill-based secondary education to young citizens that focuses on developing both academic and Social Skills, enabling them grow into being informed, sensitive, competent and active members of society is very essential. It is the gift of social, psychological and emotional stability developed at young age, which a student takes advantage of throughout his/her life. Improved Social Skills help students demonstrate strong character, build healthy relationship with others and apply right technique not only to survive but to strive and lead successful and satisfying life - personally, professionally and socially. Therefore, schools must take the first step towards materializing these ideas, by suitably integrating them into teaching-learning process using innovative and constructive strategies.

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